

ASAP

A Systemic APProach to social media
and pre-adolescents through thinking

ASAP EDUCATIONAL PROGRAMME
LEARNING UNIT

EMOTIONS

Understanding ourselves and others

Co-funded by
the European Union

EMOTIONS:
Understanding ourselves and others
LEARNING UNIT

Erasmus+ Programme

Key Action 2 - Cooperation Partnerships in School Education

ASAP - A Systemic Approach to social media and pre-adolescents through thinking skills education

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R3.2.1 ASAP Educational Programme Handbook

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Learning Unit

Emotions: Understanding ourselves and others

FOCUS OF THIS UNIT

Introduction

This learning unit focuses on developing emotional intelligence in kids through experiential activities that foster self-awareness, emotional regulation, and empathy. Emotions are also explored within the digital space, recognising the online world as a real environment where relationships and behaviours have tangible effects. The aim is to promote well-being, respectful communication, and responsible digital citizenship.

Key Competences

Key Competences* (which the Unit aims to contribute to)	
General	Specific
PERSONAL: Self-regulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Awareness and expression of personal emotions, thoughts, values, and behaviour.• Understanding and regulating personal emotions, thoughts, and behaviour, including stress responses.
PERSONAL: Flexibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Understanding and adopting new ideas, approaches, tools, and actions in response to changing contexts.• Managing transitions in personal life, social participation, work and learning pathways, while making conscious choices and setting goals
SOCIAL: Empathy	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Awareness of another person's emotions, experiences and values.• Understanding another person's emotions and experiences, and the ability to proactively take their perspective.• Responsiveness to another person's emotions and experiences.
SOCIAL: Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Awareness of the need for a variety of communication strategies, language registers, and tools that are adapted to context and content• Understanding and managing interactions and conversations in different socio-cultural contexts and domain-specific situations.

SOCIAL: Collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understanding the importance of trust, respect for human dignity and equality, coping with conflicts and negotiating disagreements to build and sustain fair and respectful relationships. Fair sharing of tasks, resources and responsibility within a group taking into account its specific aim; eliciting the expression of different views and adopting a systemic approach
LEARNING TO LEARN: Critical thinking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developing creative ideas, synthesising and combining concepts and information from different sources in view of solving problems.

**Defined according to the LifeComp and DigComp 2.2 Frameworks*

Learning outcomes

Learning outcomes	
Knowledge	Skills and Abilities
Recognizing one's own emotions and their influence on actions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identifying and managing emotions effectively.
Understanding the role of emotions in social interactions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understanding others' emotions, expressing oneself clearly, and practicing active listening.
Developing Empathy in Online Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developing empathy in online communication to better understand others' perspectives and avoid misunderstandings Developing self-regulation skills and emotional resilience to handle difficult conversations or feedback.
Identifying online spaces as real environments with risks and responsibilities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Using digital tools responsibly, protecting privacy, and critically analysing online content.
Learning ethical digital behaviour, privacy, and critical media consumption.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adapting viewpoints, evaluating personal beliefs, and fostering continuous learning. Developing original ideas, problem-solving, and implementing positive changes.
Recognizing the impact of words in communication and interpersonal relationships.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understanding the weight of words, adapting messages appropriately, and promoting respectful dialogue.

Work plan

Topic 1 – Emotions at stake

Phase 1.a (Skills development)	Activity 1.a.1 – On question...image Objective: to meet oneself, to stop for a moment to look inside oneself and then to meet the other person.	45 min
	Activity 1.a.2 – Zoom out Objective: To guide the participants to change: this is achieved when you abandon your usual patterns of thinking and try out new perspectives, stepping out of your comfort zone.	30 min
Topic 2 – The internet is also a place		
Phase 2.a (Knowledge building and skills development)	Activity 2.a.1 – Bingo Objective: To know and explore the online habits of the subjects; to map the knowledge of the characteristics of the virtual environment.	45 min
	Activity 2.a.2 – Line Play Objective: To reflect on the dissemination and publication of one's personal data (including online); to reflect on one's privacy in order to decide responsibly what we share online.	30 min
Topic 3 - Respect		
Phase 3.a (Knowledge building and skills development)	Activity 3.a.1 – Emoji Objective: to raise awareness of the complexities of communication, emphasizing how words and symbols can be interpreted differently based on context, emotions, and personal experiences.	45 min
	Activity 3.a.2 – Post-it notes Objective: to reflect on the use of words online (in comments and chats); to put oneself in the shoes of those who are offended and insulted; to raise awareness in the non-offensive use of words.	30 min
Topic 4 - Conclusion and restitution		
Phase 4.a	Activity 4.a.1 – Short video and moodboard	45 min

(Skills development)	Objective: to give participant a voice, to allow them to express what they have learnt again and to communicate, using different languages, their emotions and thoughts.	
	Activity 4.a.2 – Restitution Objective: to be able to effectively narrate complex concept by collaborating with others.	30 min

Final products

Personal Reflection Sheets: Participants create written reflections on emotions, perspectives, and experiences.

Short videos & moodboards: Creative digital summaries of learning experiences using visual storytelling.

Evaluation

Objective:

Assess the impact of the activities on the group over time.

Methods and tools:

T0–T1–T2 assessment sheets (tools provided in the annex): one set for kids (scenario-based self-assessment).

Timing:

T0 (before the intervention), T1 (immediately after), T2 (after a period of time).

Roles:

Kids complete the scenario tools.

Application contexts

The activities proposed in this unit can be used independently or combined, depending on the target group, context, and setting (e.g., school, home, workplace). The activities are designed to promote emotional awareness, effective communication, and responsible behaviour both online and offline. They can be adapted to different age groups and contexts, focusing on aspects such as emotional management, online privacy, and respectful communication. Additionally, the activities encourage critical reflection on digital habits and interpersonal relationships, fostering collaboration and creativity among participants. The structure allows for flexibility, with activities able to be tailored to specific needs and implemented in varying combinations to best suit the group dynamics and learning objectives.

Links with other LUs

- **Onlife:** connects emotional awareness with digital experiences, linking privacy, data sharing and online exposure to responsible choices.
- **Communication:** links emotions to interpersonal communication, showing how language and symbols affect feelings and interactions and supporting empathetic, assertive dialogue.

WHAT YOU NEED TO KNOW

Why emotions matter in education

Education is a matter of well-being and, therefore, of health. If happiness is understood as a state of well-being, and psychological balance helps protect health and happiness, then emotional competence becomes crucial. Research shows that individuals with developed emotional capacities are more likely to be happy and effective in life. From this perspective, the simple question “How are you?” becomes central to educational practice. Emotions are not an optional extra – they are a fundamental starting point for meaningful change in education.

Defining emotions: what are we talking about?

Daniel Goleman, in *Emotional Intelligence*, defines emotions as feelings and thoughts accompanied by psychological and biological responses, which predispose us to act in certain ways. Psychologist Paul Ekman identifies six basic emotions: anger, fear, sadness, happiness, surprise, and disgust. He later expanded this to include secondary emotions like shame, guilt, pride, and contempt. Ekman also notes that each basic emotion represents a family of related states. Goleman groups emotions into eight main families: anger, sadness, fear, joy, love, surprise, disgust, and shame.

Neuroscience and the importance of emotional intelligence

Neuroscience strongly supports the idea that emotions must be taken seriously. Research suggests that increasing self-awareness, managing negative emotions, maintaining optimism, being empathetic, and building strong social ties can all lead to a more emotionally balanced and satisfying life. These are the foundations of emotional intelligence. According to neurologist Antonio Damasio, humans possess two types of intelligence: rational and emotional. Our behaviour is influenced by both. This dual model challenges the old idea that reason should dominate emotion and instead advocates for balance and harmony between them.

Emotional intelligence can be taught

The emotional habits we learn during childhood and adolescence shape our capacity for emotional intelligence later in life. Emotional temperament is not fixed—it can be developed. Emotional intelligence consists of specific skills that anyone can learn, regardless of age, gender, or background. Through education, people can learn to use emotions constructively, gaining the ability to act deliberately rather than react impulsively. This shift—from external dependence to intentional action—is a key part of personal growth and social development.

The power of naming emotions

A central component of emotional intelligence is self-awareness: the ability to understand one’s own mood and thoughts about that mood. This awareness provides personal freedom, allowing individuals to choose how to respond in various situations. Language plays a vital role here. If someone lacks the words to describe their feelings, they cannot fully grasp or manage them. Learning to name and understand emotions gives individuals ownership over them—“if you can put into words what you feel, it belongs to you.”

Positive psychology and well-being in education

Positive psychology offers a framework for achieving well-being through gratitude, optimism, engagement, and positive relationships. These include:

- Becoming aware of one's emotions
- Practicing gratitude to focus on the positive
- Engaging in meaningful activities
- Viewing challenges as opportunities for growth
- Building strong, supportive relationships

These principles can be integrated into education and training programs designed to foster well-being. While the individual plays a central role in their own development, education can create the environment needed to support this process—particularly through encounters with others.

The critical window of adolescence

Adolescence is a key developmental period. The frontal lobes—responsible for emotional regulation, empathy, and decision-making—mature during this stage, often up to ages 16–18. Therefore, it is essential that emotional education takes place during this window. Schools and families have a responsibility to provide experiences that support emotional development before this window closes.

Emotions and life skills for health

Referring to the World Health Organization's Life Skills framework, emotional abilities like self-awareness, empathy, and emotional regulation are foundational to health-promoting behaviour. Emotional skills are not only protective—they are proactive tools for building a meaningful life. In health education, this means shifting from a narrow focus on disease and problems to a broader bio-psycho-social model that promotes human potential and flourishing

Emotional literacy as a form of prevention

The absence of emotional skills can lead to harmful behaviour, particularly in young people facing stress. Bullying and cyberbullying often arise from emotional illiteracy—an inability to read, express, or understand emotions, either in oneself or others. This deficit is common to both perpetrators and victims. Promoting emotional literacy, therefore, is a key strategy for prevention. Educational settings must prioritize emotional learning to reduce harm and increase emotional resilience.

The tools provided below adopt a preventive approach and have been designed following an animative methodology.

HOW THE UNIT WORKS

Topic 1: Emotions at stake

Through the proposed activities, the aim is to offer the opportunity to stop for a moment in life's constant rush and to think, feel and ask questions. The overall aim is to try to change one's perspective and look inside oneself; through play lead them to greater awareness (of themselves and others) and to action through the creation of new points of view. The challenge is to realise that there are different points of view and thus to be able to observe things from new angles. The methodology used exploits **visual** (photos) and **verbal stimuli that are** not directly related to each other, thus stimulating the rational and emotional systems. The activation of this inner mechanism produces **innovative responses** and lets one experience emotions and intuitions that have never been experienced before. The Internet is also an environment, and as such each person also inhabits it and experiences it with their own emotions.

What will the participants learn?

- Awareness and expression of personal emotions, thoughts, values, and behaviour.
- Understanding and regulating personal emotions, thoughts, and behaviour, including stress responses.
- Awareness of another person's emotions, experiences and values.
- Understanding another person's emotions and experiences, and the ability to proactively take their perspective.
- Responsiveness to another person's emotions and experiences.
- Developing creative ideas, synthesising and combining concepts and information from different sources in view of solving problems

Learning outcomes

Knowledge:

- Learning to recognise one's own emotions.
- Discussing emotions with others.
- Changing one's perspectives.
- Increased self-awareness.

Skills and abilities:

- Ability to identify and understand one's own emotions, distinguishing between different emotional nuances.
- Ability to manage and regulate one's emotions constructively, avoiding impulsive reactions.
- Ability to understand and share the emotions of others, fostering empathic and collaborative relationships.
- Ability to express one's own emotions clearly and respectfully, and to actively listen to the emotions of others without judgement.

- Ability to critically evaluate one's own beliefs and points of view, and to consider alternatives and new ideas.
- Ability to produce innovative responses/changes.

Space configuration

There should be ample space for participants to move around and engage with the materials, such as the photos, without disturbing others. During the initial reflection phase, participants can work individually, allowing them to focus on their personal thoughts. For the sharing and discussion portions, seating should be arranged in a circle or semi-circle to encourage open communication and interaction, making it easier for participants to exchange their perspectives and learn from one another.

Methods and pedagogical techniques

The activity emphasizes **self-reflection** and **visual learning** through the use of photos for personal expression. Participants engage in **individual work** initially, followed by a **whole-group discussion** where they share and explain their choices. **Peer learning** is encouraged as participants listen and learn from each other's experiences, while the **educator** uses **open-ended questions** to stimulate critical thinking and reflection.

Tools

- Worksheet (one per participant)
- Photos (downloaded and printed from the web)
- Pens.

Overview of the activities

Activity 1.a.1 – On question... image

Kids choose photos to answer four prompts about themselves, then share and compare perspectives to recognise multiple viewpoints and deepen self-awareness.

Activity 1.a.2 – Zoom Out

Through guided questions on selected photos, participants “zoom out” from their usual frames, exploring new angles and insights about emotions and points of view.

Detailed step-by-step instructions for these activities are provided in Activity Plan in the Annex.

Topic 2: The internet is also a place

This session helps participants reflect on the Internet as a real space where actions have real-life consequences. Through practical activities, kids are encouraged to question their habits and beliefs about the digital world, and together we build new, shared understandings of online spaces and behaviours.

What will the participants learn?

- Managing transitions in personal life, social participation, work and learning pathways, while making conscious choices and setting goals
- Awareness of another person's emotions, experiences and values.
- Understanding another person's emotions and experiences, and the ability to proactively take their perspective.
- Understanding and managing interactions and conversations in different socio-cultural contexts and domain-specific situations.
- Fair sharing of tasks, resources and responsibility within a group taking into account its specific aim; eliciting the expression of different views and adopting a systemic approach

Learning outcomes

Knowledge:

- Learning to recognise the online as a space and time of life it contains.
- Learning the rules of the virtual environment.
- Changing one's outlook.
- Producing innovative responses/change.

Skills and abilities:

- Ability to understand how technologies affect daily life and personal relationships.
- Awareness of potential risks and threats in the online space, such as privacy, security and cyberbullying.
- Ability to make responsible use of available digital resources, such as social media, online data and communication platforms.
- Ability to analyse, evaluate and solve problems in an innovative and creative way.

Space configuration

The setting requires an open space for free movement, ensuring that participants can interact easily during the Bingo activity and the crossing-the-line exercise. Desks or chairs can be pushed aside to create room for movement-based engagement. For the discussion phase, participants should be seated in a **circle or semi-circle** to encourage eye contact and open conversation. The educator positions themselves in a way that allows them to guide the discussion while remaining accessible and engaged with the group.

Methods and pedagogical techniques

The activity employs **experiential learning** through interactive games that engage participants in a dynamic and playful way. **Peer learning** is central, as participants interact to gather signatures and reflect on shared behaviours. **Active learning** techniques, such as movement-based tasks (e.g., Bingo and the crossing-the-line exercise), encourage participation and engagement. **Whole-group discussion** follows each activity, allowing for deeper reflection and analysis. The educator facilitates the process using **guided inquiry**, prompting participants to critically reflect on their digital habits, privacy, and online behaviour.

Tools

- Worksheets (one per participant)
- Pens

Overview of the activities

Activity 2.a.1 – Bingo

A movement-based bingo maps the group’s online habits and sparks discussion on the internet as a real/public space, sharing, privacy and digital permanence.

Activity 2.a.2 – Line play

Crossing an imaginary line, kids reflect on progressively personal disclosures to consider privacy and what to share responsibly online.

Detailed step-by-step instructions for this activity are provided in Activity Plan in the Annex.

Topic 3: Respect

This section invites participants to reflect on the impact of words—both compliments and insults—and how they influence emotions and interactions. Through engaging activities, they will experience firsthand how language affects others, fostering empathy and awareness in both online and offline communication. By learning to choose words carefully and considering the feelings of others, participants will develop a more conscious and responsible approach to expression, contributing to a more respectful and emotionally aware environment.

What will the participants learn?

- Awareness of another person’s emotions, experiences and values.
- Understanding another person's emotions and experiences, and the ability to proactively take their perspective.
- Responsiveness to another person’s emotions and experiences.
- Awareness of the need for a variety of communication strategies, language registers, and tools that are adapted to context and content
- Understanding and managing interactions and conversations in different socio-cultural contexts and domain-specific situations.
- Developing creative ideas, synthesising and combining concepts and information from different sources in view of solving problems.

Learning outcomes

Knowledge:

- Learning the concept of empathy
- Learning the difference in meaning we give to words, pictures, emoticons, depending on our experience (including virtual)

- Learning the value of word choice and the weight that being can have.

Skills and abilities:

- Understanding and sharing the emotions of others, developing a sense of understanding and emotional connection.
- Ability to pay attention to and understand the experiences and feelings of others without judging.
- Ability to convey clear and comprehensible messages, taking into account the context and the target audience.
- Understanding and respecting cultural differences in communication, recognising how meanings may vary according to cultural and individual context.
- Understanding non-verbal signals: Being aware of the importance of non-verbal signals, such as gestures, facial expressions and tone of voice, in the communication process.
- Ability to influence and persuade others through the effective use of words and messages.
- Reflecting on ethics and responsibility in the use of words, avoiding offensive or harmful language and promoting respectful and inclusive communication.

Space configuration

The setting should allow for movement and interaction. An open space is ideal for activities like the post-it exercise, where participants move around to exchange compliments. For the emoji-deciphering task, participants can work in pairs or small groups at tables. The final discussion should take place in a circle or semi-circle to encourage open dialogue and engagement. A visible board or wall can be used to display key reflections, reinforcing the learning outcomes. The educator should position themselves to guide the discussion while remaining approachable and interactive.

Methods and pedagogical techniques

The activities use experiential learning to help participants reflect on the impact of words in online communication. Interactive exercises, such as decoding emoji-based messages and the post-it compliment exercise, engage participants in active learning and foster peer interaction. Role-playing and guided questioning are used to enhance empathy and critical thinking, encouraging participants to consider the emotional effects of their words. The educator facilitates discussions through inquiry-based learning, prompting reflection on how language influences relationships and self-perception. Group discussions provide space for analysing misunderstandings in digital communication and the difference between intra-group and extra-group language.

Tools

- Presentation – Emoji game
- Smart Board
- Sheets
- Post-its
- Pens

Overview of the activities

Activity 3.a.1 – Emoji

Decoding emoji-only messages reveals how symbols and words can be misinterpreted without context, leading to strategies for clearer, more empathetic digital communication.

Activity 3.b.1 – Post-it notes

Exchanging compliments highlights the emotional impact of language and prompts reflection on respectful wording online and differences between in-group and public communication.

Topic 4: Conclusion and restitution

This final activity gives kids a chance to reflect on what they've learned and experienced. Working in groups helps them bring together the main ideas from the journey and express their emotions and thoughts in creative ways.

What will the participants learn?

- Awareness of another person's emotions, experiences and values.
- Understanding another person's emotions and experiences, and the ability to proactively take their perspective.
- Responsiveness to another person's emotions and experiences.
- Understanding and managing interactions and conversations in different socio-cultural contexts and domain-specific situations.
- Fair sharing of tasks, resources and responsibility within a group taking into account its specific aim; eliciting the expression of different views and adopting a systemic approach
- Developing creative ideas, synthesising and combining concepts and information from different sources in view of solving problems.

Learning outcomes

Knowledge:

- Digital skills development
- Ability to effectively synthesise and share complex concepts
- Collaboration and diversification of perspectives.

Skills and abilities:

- Ability to use digital tools effectively and consciously, including surfing the Internet, using software and applications, and managing online data.
- Ability to search, evaluate and critically use available digital resources to solve problems and achieve goals.
- Ability to express complex concepts clearly, coherently and comprehensibly, adapting language to the target audience.

- Ability to gather and integrate information from different sources to create a coherent view of a topic or problem.
- Knowledge and mastery of digital tools and platforms that facilitate the synthesis and sharing of information, such as presentations, infographics and videos.
- Ability to collaborate effectively with other individuals towards common goals, sharing ideas, resources and responsibilities.
- Ability to critically evaluate different perspectives and opinions, analysing evidence and considering arguments from different angles.

Space configuration

An open, flexible space is necessary for group work, providing access to digital tools and areas for brainstorming and collaboration. Seating should be arranged in a circle or semi-circle for presentations, fostering open communication. The educator should remain centrally positioned to guide discussions and provide support, ensuring an interactive and collaborative environment.

Methods and pedagogical techniques

The activities focus on collaborative and experiential learning, encouraging participants to work in small groups to create digital content (Reels or Moodboards) that express their emotions and ideas. This promotes teamwork, creativity, and critical thinking. The educator facilitates the process with inquiry-based learning, guiding participants to reflect on their choices and the themes they are exploring. Group presentations and peer feedback stimulate further discussion and reflection, enhancing communication and self-expression skills.

Tools

- PC / Tablet / Smartphone
- Smart board
- Design platform (like Canva)

Overview of the activities

Activity 4.a.1 – Short video and moodboard

Small groups create short reels or moodboards to express what they learned and felt, then discuss choices and messages.

Activity 4.a.2 – Restitution

Groups present their products and narrate the process, engaging peers in questions and shared reflection.

Evaluation tools

To evaluate the achievement of the learning outcomes related to the development of skills, the following tool is proposed for use with the kids. This activity should be proposed at three different stages: before the learning pathway (T0), at the end of the pathway (T1), and after a period of time has passed (T2), in order to evaluate both immediate and long-term impact.

WHERE DOES IT HAPPEN?

Indicate for each situation in which place (physical or virtual) you can face, in your opinion, that discussion/topic.

Arguing with a friend of yours for a heavy offense received	Tell how your day went
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> In person at home <input type="radio"/> In person in a public place <input type="radio"/> School break <input type="radio"/> Group chat <input type="radio"/> Private chat <input type="radio"/> IG history <input type="radio"/> IG story (close friends only) <input type="radio"/> Reel/Video TikTok <input type="radio"/> Comment below a video/post/story <input type="radio"/> Group video call <input type="radio"/> Private video call <input type="radio"/> Call <input type="radio"/> IG personal notes <input type="radio"/> Live social 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> In person at home <input type="radio"/> In person in a public place <input type="radio"/> School break <input type="radio"/> Group chat <input type="radio"/> Private chat <input type="radio"/> IG history <input type="radio"/> IG story (close friends only) <input type="radio"/> Reel/Video TikTok <input type="radio"/> Comment below a video/post/story <input type="radio"/> Group video call <input type="radio"/> Private video call <input type="radio"/> Call <input type="radio"/> IG personal notes <input type="radio"/> Live social
Make a nice joke to a friend of yours	Share moments of intimacy with your boyfriend/girlfriend
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> In person at home <input type="radio"/> In person in a public place <input type="radio"/> School break <input type="radio"/> Group chat <input type="radio"/> Private chat <input type="radio"/> IG history <input type="radio"/> IG story (close friends only) <input type="radio"/> Reel/Video TikTok <input type="radio"/> Comment below a video/post/story <input type="radio"/> Group video call <input type="radio"/> Private video call <input type="radio"/> Call <input type="radio"/> IG personal notes <input type="radio"/> Live social 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> In person at home <input type="radio"/> In person in a public place <input type="radio"/> School break <input type="radio"/> Group chat <input type="radio"/> Private chat <input type="radio"/> IG history <input type="radio"/> IG story (close friends only) <input type="radio"/> Reel/Video TikTok <input type="radio"/> Comment below a video/post/story <input type="radio"/> Group video call <input type="radio"/> Private video call <input type="radio"/> Call <input type="radio"/> IG personal notes <input type="radio"/> Live social

Complaining about a low grade taken unfairly	To Confide a secret to a friend
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> In person at home <input type="radio"/> In person in a public place <input type="radio"/> School break <input type="radio"/> Group chat <input type="radio"/> Private chat <input type="radio"/> IG history <input type="radio"/> IG story (close friends only) <input type="radio"/> Reel/Video TikTok <input type="radio"/> Comment below a video/post/story <input type="radio"/> Group video call <input type="radio"/> Private video call <input type="radio"/> Call <input type="radio"/> IG personal notes <input type="radio"/> Live social 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> In person at home <input type="radio"/> In person in a public place <input type="radio"/> School break <input type="radio"/> Group chat <input type="radio"/> Private chat <input type="radio"/> IG history <input type="radio"/> IG story (close friends only) <input type="radio"/> Reel/Video TikTok <input type="radio"/> Comment below a video/post/story <input type="radio"/> Group video call <input type="radio"/> Private video call <input type="radio"/> Call <input type="radio"/> IG personal notes <input type="radio"/> Live social
Apologizing for a wrong	Tell HOW YOU FEEL at that moment
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> In person at home <input type="radio"/> In person in a public place <input type="radio"/> School break <input type="radio"/> Group chat <input type="radio"/> Private chat <input type="radio"/> IG history <input type="radio"/> IG story (close friends only) <input type="radio"/> Reel/Video TikTok <input type="radio"/> Comment below a video/post/story <input type="radio"/> Group video call <input type="radio"/> Private video call <input type="radio"/> Call <input type="radio"/> IG personal notes <input type="radio"/> Live social 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> In person at home <input type="radio"/> In person in a public place <input type="radio"/> School break <input type="radio"/> Group chat <input type="radio"/> Private chat <input type="radio"/> IG history <input type="radio"/> IG story (close friends only) <input type="radio"/> Reel/Video TikTok <input type="radio"/> Comment below a video/post/story <input type="radio"/> Group video call <input type="radio"/> Private video call <input type="radio"/> Call <input type="radio"/> IG personal notes <input type="radio"/> Live social

ACTIVITY PLANS & WORKSHEETS

Activity 1.a.1 – ON QUESTION... IMAGE

Objective

- To meet oneself, to pause and look inside, and then to encounter others.
- The activity helps participants recognise their own emotions and perspectives and discover the diversity of viewpoints in the group.

Preparation

- Arrange the room so participants can move freely to look at images (tables, floor, or walls).
- Print and spread out a selection of varied photos (landscapes, people, abstract, objects).
- Prepare worksheets with four questions, one per participant:
 - Where are you now?
 - How are you online?
 - What do you want to say to today's you?
 - How do you see your future?
- Provide pens and space for writing answers under each chosen image.
- Ensure a calm atmosphere that supports reflection (soft background music optional).

Step-by-step instructions

1. Introduction (5 minutes)

- Welcome the group and explain that the activity is about exploring personal emotions and perspectives using images.
 - Stress that there are no right or wrong answers—choices depend on each person's feelings in the moment.
-

2. Individual work (15 minutes)

- Give each participant a worksheet with the four questions.
 - Ask them to move around the room, look at the displayed photos, and choose one image per question.
 - After selecting, they glue or note the chosen picture on their worksheet and briefly write down why it represents their answer.
 - Mention that images can be shared—if two participants like the same photo, they can both use it.
-

3. Sharing in the group (25 minutes)

- Gather everyone in a circle.
 - Each participant presents their four chosen images and explains their choices.
 - The educator can guide sharing either question by question (all answer Q1, then Q2...) or participant by participant.
 - Use open prompts like: *“What made you choose this picture?”* or *“What emotions does this image express for you?”*
-

4. Highlighting multiple perspectives (5 minutes)

- After sharing, underline that everyone’s answers show different but equally valid perspectives.
- Point out similarities and differences, noting how seeing others’ views can broaden one’s own

Concluding the activity (10 minutes)

1. Recap of the key learnings

- Emotions shape how we see ourselves and others.
 - Different perspectives coexist and enrich our understanding.
 - Recognising
-

2. Personal reflection

- Ask participants to think silently about:
 - Which image spoke to me the most today?
 - Did I discover something new about myself?
 - Give them 1–2 minutes to jot down one sentence on their worksheet as a takeaway.
-

3. Group sharing

- Invite a few volunteers to share their takeaway sentence with the group.
 - Emphasise listening respectfully and noticing connections between personal reflections.
-

4. Reinforce the takeaway

End with a short message (on board or projector):

“Every picture tells a story. By sharing ours, we learn to see ourselves more clearly and to understand others more deeply.”

Optional next steps

Emotion Journal:

Encourage participants to start a journal where they reflect on their emotions by attaching images or drawing visuals that represent how they feel each day.

**WHERE ARE
YOU NOW?**

**WHAT DOES IT
MEAN TO YOU?**

**HOW DO YOU
FEEL ONLINE?**

**HOW DO YOU SEE
YOUR FUTURE SELF?**

Activity 1.a.2 – ZOOM OUT

Objective

- To guide participants to step outside their usual patterns of thinking and explore new perspectives. By “zooming out,” participants practice observing familiar things from different angles, fostering curiosity, empathy, and openness to change.

Preparation

- Use the same set of photos from Activity 1.a.1 (participants keep the ones they previously selected).
- Prepare guiding questions on slips of paper or on a projector/board:
 - Who do you think took that photo?
 - What emotions does it arouse in you?
 - What happened before and after the captured instant?
 - What is around that image, outside the frame?
- Arrange chairs in a circle for discussion.
- Provide pens and paper for additional notes or reflections.

Step-by-step instructions

1. Introduction (5 minutes)

- Explain that the activity is about looking at things from a wider angle, noticing what we often overlook.
- Emphasise that the goal is not to find “correct” answers but to explore multiple possibilities.

2. Individual exploration (10 minutes)

- Ask participants to take their chosen images from Activity 1.a.1.
 - Invite them to reflect individually on the guiding questions (noting down short answers).
-

3. Group discussion (20 minutes)

- In a circle, participants share their reflections.
 - Encourage them to compare how different people perceive the same image.
 - Use probing prompts: *“What do you notice that others might not?”*, *“How would your view change if you were the photographer?”*
-

4. Connecting insights (10 minutes)

- Guide the group to notice patterns: some perspectives might converge, others may differ widely.
- Highlight that expanding our viewpoint helps us better understand ourselves, others, and the complexity of emotions.

Concluding the activity (10 minutes)

1. Recap of the key learnings

- By “zooming out,” we discover that our usual view is only one of many possible perspectives.
- Emotions influence how we interpret situations and images.
- Openness to alternative perspectives strengthens empathy and creativity.

2. Personal reflection

- Ask participants to write down: “One new perspective I discovered today is...”
- Encourage them to think about how this perspective might help in their daily life.

3. Group sharing

- Invite a few volunteers to share their reflection.
- Point out the diversity of answers, reinforcing that there is no single way to interpret an experience.

4. Reinforce the takeaway

- Close with a visual metaphor: show a zoomed-in picture, then the full image, illustrating how context changes meaning.
- End with the message: “When we step back, we don’t lose focus—we gain understanding.”

Optional next steps

- Invite participants to apply the “zoom out” approach to a real-life challenge: before reacting, pause and ask themselves, “What else could be going on here?”
- Suggest keeping a reflection journal where they write down one situation each week in which they practiced seeing things from a new perspective.
- Encourage creating a group photo project: take ordinary photos and write multiple captions showing different interpretations.

Activity 2.a.1 – BINGO

Objective

- To explore how the internet functions as a space where people interact, build relationships, and share emotions.
 - To help students reflect on their own online habits and how they relate to others in digital environments.
 - To encourage a discussion about online safety, empathy, and respectful behaviour.
-

Preparation

Materials:

- Printable Bingo cards for students – see the Worksheet 1 (one per participant).
- Pens or markers.

Room setup:

- Arrange the classroom to allow students to move around easily and talk to their peers.
-

Step-by-step instructions

1. Introduction (5 minutes)

- Set the scene.
 - Explain: "Today, we're going to play a game to learn more about how we all behave online. The internet is like a shared space where we all interact, so this activity will help us explore our similarities and differences."
- Hand out the Bingo worksheets and pens.
 - Explain: The worksheet has 25 boxes, each with a different behaviour or experience related to the internet. Your task is to walk around the room and find classmates who match each behaviour. When you find someone, ask them to tick or sign the box. The goal is to complete the entire worksheet as quickly as possible. The first person to complete their sheet and shout "Bingo!" wins.

2. Playing the game (20 minutes)

- **Start the game (20 minutes):**
 - Allow students to walk around the room, interact with classmates, and ask questions.
 - Monitor the activity to ensure students are engaging respectfully and fairly.

3. Group reflection (15 minutes)

- **Declare the winner:**
 - Once a student completes their sheet, confirm their answers (e.g., ask a few classmates to verify if they signed their boxes).
 - Celebrate their win with a small prize or applause.
- **Ask the following questions:**
 - What did you learn about your classmates during this activity?
 - Were there any behaviours or experiences that surprised you?
 - Were there any boxes that were difficult to find someone for? Why do you think that is?
- **Highlight any common themes or unique behaviours across the class.**

Concluding the activity (10 minutes)

1. Recap of the key learnings

- Online spaces are real environments where actions have real consequences.
- Every interaction (likes, posts, comments) leaves a trace and contributes to digital identity.
- Awareness of our habits helps us make safer and more responsible choices.

2. Personal reflection

Ask participants to write down one answer to:

- *“What is one thing I share online that I might want to reconsider?”*

3. Group sharing

- Invite volunteers to share reflections.
 - Emphasise that experiences vary, and there are many ways to approach online behaviour responsibly.
-

4. Reinforce the takeaway

End with a short message on the board/projector:

“If you share it online, it’s no longer just yours. Think twice before you click.”

Optional next steps

- Suggest that participants discuss with their family which online habits feel safe and which may need adjustment.
- Encourage creating a “Digital Habits Map” at home: list apps used, note what data is shared, and reflect on which practices feel comfortable or risky.
- Link to the next activity (*Line play*), which deepens reflection on privacy and personal information online.

Learning Unit: Emotions
Activity 2a1 – BINGO
Worksheet

Task:
 Find classmates who match each behaviour. When you find someone, ask them to tick or sign the box.

He/she has a social media profile followed by over 300 followers.	He/she plays online video games every day.	He/she has a social media profile (including WhatsApp).	He/she checks his smartphone every 10 minutes to see if he has received notifications.	He/she has argued with someone online.
He/she did a live stream.	He/she participated in a challenge.	He/she lied about his age online.	He/she has experienced or witnessed episodes of cyberbullying.	He/she watches videos on YouTube.
He/she took a screenshot.	He/she owns a personal smartphone.	A photo/post he/she published received more than 150 likes.	He/she knows what PEGI is.	He/she browses the internet without adult supervision.
He/she sent a very personal selfie to someone.	He/she goes online to study or research.	He/she has come into contact with strangers in game chat.	He/she has shared photos or videos at least once in a WhatsApp group.	He/she sends more than 50 messages a day on WhatsApp.
He/she made in-game purchases.	He/she is part of one or more WhatsApp groups.	He/she often uses his smartphone in bed at night.	He/she enjoys posting his videos on TikTok.	He/she has posted/sent/shared a photo or video online that he later regretted.

Activity 2.a.2 – LINE PLAY

Objective

- To reflect on the dissemination and publication of personal data online and to consider privacy issues in order to make responsible decisions about what to share.
-

Preparation

- Clear a large space in the room where participants can move freely.
 - Use tape or chalk to mark an imaginary line on the floor.
 - Prepare a list of progressively personal questions (from general habits to more sensitive information).
 - Arrange chairs in a circle for the concluding reflection.
-

Step-by-step instructions

1. Introduction (5 minutes)

- Explain that this activity is about thinking carefully about how much personal information we reveal and what it means to share it—both in person and online.
- Stress that crossing the line is voluntary: participants only cross if they feel comfortable.

2. Crossing the line (20 min)

- All participants stand on one side of the line.
- The educator asks a series of questions. Each time, those who answer “yes” cross the line.
 - Examples of questions (in increasing sensitivity):
 - Who watched a TV series last weekend?
 - Who plays sports?
 - Who owns a smartphone?

- Who has at least one social profile?
 - Who has ever shared their location online?
 - Who is in love? (optionally followed by “Who wants to say their name?”)
- After each crossing, the educator pauses briefly and invites volunteers to explain their choice if they wish.
-

3. Guided reflection (10 minutes)

- After the activity, the group returns to a circle.
- The educator leads a discussion with questions such as:

“What did you feel when deciding whether to cross or not?”

“Which questions felt easy to answer, and which felt too personal?”

“What would it mean if these answers were published online for everyone to see?”

4. Link to digital context (5 minutes)

- Highlight that sharing online is similar to crossing the line: once information is shared, others can see it, and it may stay available permanently.
 - Reinforce the idea of choosing carefully what to share and protecting privacy.
-

Concluding the activity (10 minutes)

1. Recap of the key learnings

- Not all information is safe or necessary to share.
 - Privacy is a personal choice, but online sharing often goes beyond our control.
 - Critical thinking helps us decide when to cross the “line” and when to hold back.
-

2. Personal reflection

Ask participants to write down: *“One thing I learned about myself and sharing today is...”*

3. Group sharing

- Invite a few volunteers to share their reflection.

- Emphasise that everyone’s comfort level is different, and that respecting others’ boundaries is part of online and offline respect.
-

4. Reinforce the takeaway

Conclude with a short message on the board/projector:

“Crossing the line in real life is a choice. Online, the line is permanent—think before you share.”

Optional next steps

- Encourage participants to review the privacy settings on their social media accounts and make at least one change to increase their control over personal data.
- Suggest a family discussion about online privacy: what each member shares, what feels safe, and what should remain private.
- Invite the group to create posters or infographics about “safe sharing rules” to display in class or online.

Activity 3.a.1 – EMOJI

Objective

- To raise awareness of the challenges of digital communication, highlighting how words and symbols (like emojis) can be interpreted differently depending on context, emotions, and personal experiences.
- The activity helps participants reflect on the importance of clarity and empathy in online communication.

Preparation

- Prepare a set of emoji-only “sentences” (3–5 examples) to present on a smart board, projector, or handouts. Each sequence should allow multiple interpretations.
- Provide each participant with paper and pens.
- Arrange chairs in a classroom or circle setting to allow both individual work and group reflection.

Step-by-step instructions

1. Introduction (5 minutes)

- Explain the purpose: to explore how we communicate online and how easily messages can be misunderstood.
- Give a short example: show an emoji sequence and ask the group for quick interpretations. Highlight the variety of responses.

2. Deciphering emoji messages (10 minutes)

- Present each emoji-only sentence one at a time.
 - Participants write down what they think the message means.
 - Encourage them to work individually at first, to compare answers later.
-

3. Revealing intended meanings (10 minutes)

- Reveal the “intended” meaning of each emoji sentence.
 - Participants check their answers, noticing where their interpretation differed.
 - Most will find they misinterpreted at least one sentence — this is part of the learning.
-

4. Group reflection (15 minutes)

Facilitate a discussion with prompts:

- *“Why do you think some messages were easier or harder to understand?”*
- *“What happens in real online conversations when messages are misunderstood?”*
- *“Have you ever had a conflict online because of miscommunication?”*

Highlight the absence of non-verbal cues (tone, body language, facial expression) in digital spaces.

5. Strategies for clear communication (5 minutes)

Present three guidelines:

1. Think before you write — consider clarity.
 2. Choose words carefully, especially in online settings.
 3. Consider the recipient’s perspective — how might they interpret it?
-

Concluding the activity (10 minutes)

1. Recap of the key learnings

- Emojis and symbols are open to multiple interpretations.
 - Misunderstandings are common online due to lack of tone and context.
 - Careful wording and empathy improve communication.
-

2. Personal reflection

- Ask participants to write down: *“One thing I will do differently in my online communication is...”*
-

3. Group sharing

- Invite volunteers to share their reflections.
 - Emphasise the value of learning from each other’s experiences.
-

4. Reinforce the takeaway

End with a message on the board/projector:

“Behind every emoji or word is a person with feelings. Communicate to connect, not to confuse.”

Optional next steps

- Invite participants to create their own emoji messages and exchange them in pairs, testing how well they can be understood.
- Suggest that students keep a “digital diary” of misunderstandings they encounter online during the week and reflect on how they could be avoided.
- Connect to the next activity (*Post-it notes*), which explores the emotional impact of words even more directly.

EMOJI

Learning Unit: Emotions

Activity 3a1 - Emoji

Presentation

Something easy to start with 😊

Movie

Harry Potter

Movie

Finding Nemo

Movie

Ratatouille

Finding classmates' qualities

As wise as an owl

Finding classmates' qualities

As busy as a bee

Finding classmates' qualities

As slow as a snail

Finding classmates' qualities

As quiet as a mouse

Finding a proverb

Don't cry over spilled milk

Finding a proverb

An apple a day keeps the doctor away

Finding a saying

It's raining cats and dogs

Now for something harder! 😊
Write your answers down on
paper.

What sentence is hidden behind
these emojis?

Correct answers

To play with fire

Hard words / thoughts

Words can hurt

Watching the X-Factor on TV

Think before you speak

Choose the right words

Activity 3.b.1 - POST-IT NOTES

Objective

- To reflect on the use of words online (in comments and chats), to put oneself in the shoes of those who are offended or insulted, and to raise awareness about choosing non-offensive and respectful language.

Preparation

- Provide each participant with 4 post-it notes and a pen.
- Arrange chairs in a circle or semi-circle, with enough open space for participants to move around and exchange notes.
- Prepare a board or wall to display reflections later (optional).
- Briefly discuss the difference between compliments and insults, steering focus toward positive, genuine compliments about character traits (not appearance).

Step-by-step instructions

1. Introduction (5 minutes)

- Explain that the activity explores the impact of words: how they can uplift or hurt.
- Clarify that compliments should focus on personality or actions (e.g., kindness, helpfulness, creativity) rather than looks.

2. Writing compliments (10 minutes)

- Each participant writes 4 compliments on post-it notes.
- Encourage them to think about qualities they admire in others.

3. Exchanging compliments (15 minutes)

- Participants place one post-it on the arm of the person to their right, one on the arm of the person to their left.
- The remaining two post-its can be given to anyone in the group.
- After exchanging, each participant collects the compliments they received and attaches them to their chair or keeps them visible.

4. Reflection on experience (15 minutes)

- Ask participants:
 - *“How do you feel wearing compliments?”*
 - *“What if these were insults instead — how would you feel?”*

5. Exploring language contexts (10 minutes)

- Discuss intra-group language (private jokes, familiar talk with friends) vs. extra-group/public language (online, visible to strangers).
- Highlight how online comments can be misinterpreted or cause harm beyond the original intention.

Concluding the activity (10 minutes)

1. Recap of the key learnings

- Words carry emotional weight — they can strengthen or damage relationships.
- Compliments build confidence, while insults can cause long-lasting harm.
- Online, words spread further and last longer.

2. Personal reflection

- Ask participants to write down: *“One way I can use words more positively online is...”*

3. Group sharing

- Invite a few volunteers to share their reflections.
- Emphasise how respect in communication contributes to safer, kinder online spaces.

4. Reinforce the takeaway

- End with a short message on the board/projector:
“Words are powerful. Use them to lift others up, not to tear them down.”

Optional next steps

- Suggest that participants keep one of their received compliments in their notebook as a reminder of the value of kind words.
- Encourage the group to start a “compliment wall” in class, where positive messages can be posted anonymously over time.
- Link to the conclusion activities (Short video and Restitution), where participants will creatively reflect on what they learned.

Activity 4.a.1 - SHORT VIDEO AND MOODBOARD

Objective

- To give participants a voice and allow them to creatively express what they have learned.
- By producing a short video (reel) or moodboard, participants reflect on their emotions, perspectives, and insights, and communicate them using multiple expressive languages (visuals, text, sound).

Preparation

- Divide participants into small groups (3–4 people).
- Provide access to digital tools (PCs, tablets, or smartphones).
- Ensure internet connection and access to a free design platform such as **Canva** (recommended) or another suitable tool.
- Prepare basic instructions on copyright-free images and content use.
- Arrange the space with separate working areas for each group.
- Ensure consent forms if participants appear in photos/videos (recommended: avoid filming minors' faces).

Step-by-step instructions

1. Introduction (5 minutes)

- Explain that the goal is to summarise the learning journey creatively.
- Clarify product options:
 - A short vertical video (1–2 minutes, similar to Instagram reels).
 - A moodboard: a digital collage of images and words expressing main insights.
- Emphasise freedom of expression — groups may choose different formats.

2. Group work: creating the product (25 minutes)

- Participants brainstorm ideas: which emotions, insights, or lessons stood out most?
- They collect images, keywords, and short texts.
- They design their short video or moodboard collaboratively.
- The educator circulates, offering technical and creative support.

3. Presentation of products (15 minutes)

- Each group presents their video or moodboard to the class.
- They briefly explain their choices: why they selected certain images, words, or music.

4. Peer feedback (15 minutes)

- Invite the rest of the group to react with positive feedback.
 - Highlight creativity, clarity of message, and emotional impact.
-

Concluding the activity (10 minutes)

1. Recap of the key learnings

- Reflecting creatively helps consolidate what we have learned.
 - Digital tools can be used to express emotions and perspectives responsibly.
 - Sharing in groups highlights diversity of experiences.
-

2. Personal reflection

- Ask each participant to write down: *“What is one message from our video/moodboard that I personally want to remember.”*
-

3. Group sharing

- Invite one representative from each group to share their reflection with the class.
-

4. Reinforce the takeaway

- End with a closing message on the board/projector:
“Creativity is a bridge between learning and expression. What we create together stays with us.”
-

Optional next steps

- Collect all videos and moodboards into a shared digital gallery and make it accessible to participants.
- Encourage students to present their products to parents or other classes as part of dissemination.
- Use the materials later in **Activity 4.a.2 – Restitution** as the basis for collaborative storytelling.

Activity 4.a.2 – RESTITUTION

Objective

- To give participants a voice and allow them to creatively express what they have learned.
- By producing a short video (reel) or moodboard, participants reflect on their emotions, perspectives, and insights, and communicate them using multiple expressive languages (visuals, text, sound).

Preparation

- Ensure that the products from Activity 4.a.1 (videos, moodboards) are ready to present.
- Arrange the room with chairs in a semi-circle or classroom presentation setup.
- Provide projector/smart board or wall space for displaying videos and moodboards.
- Prepare a few guiding reflection questions to stimulate discussion.

Step-by-step instructions

1. Introduction (5 minutes)

- Explain that this final activity is about *restitution*: giving back to the group by sharing what was learned.
- Emphasise that everyone's work and reflections are valuable pieces of the collective journey.

2. Group presentations (25 minutes)

- Each group presents their video or moodboard.
- They explain the process:
 - Why did we choose this theme?
 - How did we decide on images, words, or sounds?
 - What message did we want to communicate?

3. Discussion and questions (15 minutes)

- After each presentation, invite questions from peers.
- Encourage respectful dialogue and curiosity about differences in perspectives.
- Use prompts such as:
 - *“What surprised you in this presentation?”*
 - *“Which part of this video/moodboard resonated with you most?”*

4. Synthesis (10 minutes)

- The educator summarises recurring themes: emotions, respect, online behaviour, new perspectives.
 - Highlight how the products show both individual creativity and group collaboration.
-

Concluding the activity (10 minutes)

1. Recap of the key learnings

- Expressing ideas through creative products deepens understanding.
- Collaboration allows multiple voices to come together into a shared narrative.
- Presenting to others strengthens communication and reflection skills.

2. Personal reflection

- Ask each participant to write down: *“The most important thing I am taking away from this programme is...”*

3. Group sharing

- Invite several participants to share their reflections with the whole group.
- Emphasise appreciation for the variety of answers.

4. Reinforce the takeaway

- End with a final collective message (projected or spoken together):
“Our words, choices, and emotions shape the world we live in — offline and online.”

Optional next steps

- Compile all videos/moodboards into a shared digital portfolio as a final record of the project.
- Encourage participants to share their reflections with parents, teachers, or peers outside the group.
- Use insights from the activity to inspire follow-up projects on emotional intelligence and digital responsibility.

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